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DESIGNING FOR THE REAL CHILD TOY DESIGNERS AND PSYCHOLOGISTS IN DIALOGUE ON REVERSAL THEORY

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ABSTRACT

The social sciences constitute a rich potential source of theoretical contexts for understanding human behaviour, not all of which are easily accessible to designers. Dialogue between social scientists and designers should, therefore, improve design outcomes. Within the setting of a course on design for children's play, such a dialogue between psychologists and design students was organized around Reversal Theory, a psychological theory that describes relations between arousal levels and hedonic tone underlying the experience of situations. This theory has been little explored in design. The project showed that psychologists and designers were, through discussion, able to connect theory to practical implications for design by entering each other's domain, and by discussing design ideas as carriers of psychological concepts. The paper reflects on, and supports, the value of Reversal Theory for toy design and should be seen as just one example of the value of sustained direct dialogue between the social sciences and design.

Keywords: design methodology, psychology, design for play, Reversal Theory

INTRODUCTION

When developing design ideas for children's play, designers generally aim to take a broad perspective that encompasses not just the child, but also their families and society and includes a broad range of intended outcomes from simply 'having fun' to communicating values. Turning to the social sciences as a source of design inspiration and information is an obvious step to take.

Previous experiences with education on design for children's play have shown that design students with little background in child psychology are apt to build an inner collage from fragmented knowledge that is a misrepresentation of what real children are like (Gielen, 2010). Lack of empathy with children is referred to as a source of this misinterpretation; lack of knowledge of the theories involved at an appropriate degree of depth is another likely cause. Different disciplines tend to speak different languages and it may be that some of the concepts and methods of social science are relatively inaccessible to designers. This may explain the apparently disproportionate influence of a relatively narrow range of social science theories on design for play. It also suggests that dialogue between designers and social scientists could facilitate the translation process and so enlarge the design space available to toy designers. An earlier exploration of the potential of this dialogic approach using Winnicott's psychoanalytical theory of transitional objects and spaces (Van Leeuwen & Westwood, 2010) provided the stimulus for the present project.

In the following, 'toy design' is used to refer to the design of all virtual and physical objects, equipment, spaces and landscapes that are intended to facilitate children's playful experiences.

RESEARCH THEME

A variety of theoretical approaches may be valuable sources of new creative input, it may lead designers to discover new perspectives on the behaviour and needs of their intended users. On the basis that the social sciences constitute a rich potential source of

such new theoretical contexts, and given that this is not the natural terrain for designers, one would expect that a life dialogue between social scientists and designers results in better design outcomes. This paper describes a project in which psychologists worked with design students to make psychological concepts more accessible and usable. In this case the potential of 'Reversal Theory' (Kerr & Apter, 1991; Apter, 2007) to inspire and inform toy design was explored. The aim was to gain insight in how students without a psychology background could appropriate the theory and how the interaction between the social science and design profession could be shaped to support the application of this theory within design.

REVERSAL THEORY

Reversal Theory follows a phenomenological (i.e. experiential) approach describing fluctuating motivational states which underlie our everyday behaviour. One aspect of the theory describes the reversal (or switch) between a goal-directed, telic state and a playful, paratelic state. Depending on the prevailing state a given level of arousal would be experienced quite differently. For example, Figure 1 shows how low arousal is experienced as pleasant relaxation in a goal-directed *telic* state but is experienced unpleasantly as boredom in a playful or *paratelic* state.

Figure 1: Telic and paratelic curves of experiencing arousal.

High arousal is experienced as anxiety in a telic and as excitement in a paratelic mode. The goal-

directedness of the telic mode (e.g. solving a problem in an examination or dealing with an injury) means that behaviours tend towards arousal-avoidance in order to secure the goal. In this case obstacles or barriers to the goal increase arousal resulting in experiences of frustration and anxiety. Alternatively, in a paratelic mode, a person is motivated by the engagement in an activity more than its outcome and so behaviours tend toward increasing arousal which is experienced as excitement. Immersion in play activities or the indulgence in extreme sports such as sky diving or rock climbing are main examples. Arousal levels fluctuate on a moment to moment basis and how they are experienced depends upon the prevailing state (telic or paratelic); during the course of the day there may be numerous reversals between the two modes.

Reversals occur for many reasons e.g. when the interpretation of a situation changes from fun to threatening. Take the example of consecutive moments of experiencing a rollercoaster ride: while queuing one may get excited at the prospect of the ride, then anxious on hearing the screams of those racing by in the carts, then comforted by the sturdy safety brackets, exhilarated by the beautiful view from the top, terrified by the experience of free fall, and finally thrilled at surviving this ride over which you have had no control. Individuals differ from each other in their preference for the telic or paratelic mode and in the interpretation of situations as dangerous or exciting. In other words different individuals are more or less playful and are more or less likely to embrace danger. When in a paratelic or playful mode, individuals seek excitement to differing degrees. The rollercoaster example suggests that the powerful arousers (e.g. loud noises, speed) that are often also associated with anxiety in the telic mode, can, if experienced in the paratelic mode, achieve the rewards of exhilaration and excitement. This is, therefore, a useful idea for toy design. Kerr and Apter (1991) discern seven ways to stimulate arousal and increase excitement in this mode (Table 1).

The distinction that Reversal Theory makes between goal-oriented, serious activities and action-oriented playful ones, where means become more relevant

than ends, make it relevant for understanding children's experience of play. Design for play at all ages also needs to be aware of and accommodate individual differences and the possible changes in motivational mode. Yet, little attention has been given to this specific concept by designers. Reversal Theory is popular in areas such as sports sciences, where it gives a basis for enhancing motivation in sportsmen with various motivational styles. Reversal Theory has been used in the context of adult play (e.g. Kerr & Apter, 1991) and its more extreme, often negativistic, forms of sensation seeking behaviour. Ford (2003) investigated children's motivational styles in learning at school using a Reversal Theory approach. But we have been unable to find any evidence of the theory being used to inform design for children's play. M.J. Apter (personal communication, September 13, 2009) has confirmed the void and welcomed this initiative.

REVERSAL THEORY AND TOY DESIGN

In short the reasons to choose Reversal Theory as input for the design dialogue were:

- It is a phenomenological concept, i.e. focusing on experience rather than performance. This means it focuses on what makes people play rather than what developmental task is achieved through play. As many students before had taken a developmental approach to toy design, this seemed an important different perspective to offer.
- It addresses processes of change rather than static states of being. This was thought to help students in thinking about how play evolves - within each continuous period of play as well as over time, and how complexity of playful behaviour evolves with it.
- It gives a holistic perspective on behaviour,

addressing behaviour in general. But at the same time, it strongly focuses on subjectivity and individual differences.

- It can be applied to any age group. Students in earlier projects tended to look for a list of what is interesting and suitable at what age. However, Reversal Theory provides a far more subtle approach where the combination of competency and preferred levels of arousal determine a range of play preferences.

Students designing toys often determine the goals of their design in terms of funny, exciting, challenging, rewarding, etc. These emerge during the play process rather than that they are objective elements of the toy and its intended use and therefore need a theoretic framework to bring meaning to it. Reversal Theory offers a framework that helps to translate these abstract requirements into concrete design elements supporting specific possibilities for action.

METHODOLOGY

The project described in this paper followed a research through design approach, in which the application of theory was observed in practice. The theory was introduced within the educational setting of a Master course on design for children's play; it was used in three consecutive editions of the course. At first it was introduced in a formal theoretical lecture. Then, in an iterative process, a total of 20 design students (10 teams of two students) applied the theory within their design assignment. Another 40 students were not formally instructed to apply the theory but did receive lectures and participated in the dialogue with both a design coach and two psychologists about it.

As the course was aimed at children's play, the students were asked to design for an age group anywhere from 0 to 14 years. No exact age group

Strategy	Explanation and/or examples
Exposure to arousing stimulation	Sounds and lights, complex views that provide puzzlement and interest
Fiction and narrative	Emotionally bonding with (fictional) characters
Challenge	Overcoming difficulties and frustrations, often in the face of others
Exploration	Moving into new territory - literally or metaphorically
Negativism	Deliberate and provocative rule-breaking
Cognitive synergy	Simultaneous experience of incompatible properties in relation to a given identity
Facing danger	Physical or psychological threats

Table 1. Seven strategies for stimulating arousal, as described by Kerr and Apter (1991)

was determined, to offer the students freedom of choice but also to do justice to the age-independent nature of Reversal Theory.

For the analysis, a variety of outputs from the students was collected: oral and written questions, summaries of the theories, design proposals (both in drawings and in text) and their self-assessments of the quality of their final design. In all these, signs of understanding and limitations thereof were observed and discussed among the design coach and psychologists.

No formal assessment of the design concepts was made (e.g. comparison to design concepts made with more traditional input). It was thought that, within the educational setting, the many known and unknown influences and differences between students would not allow any sensible conclusions to be drawn. It was however observed if and how the developing understanding of the theory influenced the design path of each student team.

All these observations and outputs were then clustered into themes on the basis that each theme represents a general situation encountered by several student groups and contributes to our aim of understanding how to make psychological concepts more accessible and usable.

FINDINGS

Below are the seven themes that emerged from the clustering of observations and outputs. They represent the general tendencies in the process of familiarising with and utilising the theory, its interaction with the design process and the design results. The findings are illustrated with some examples from the design projects.

DESIGN AS DIALOGUE

The dominant finding of this explorative project is the bi-directional nature of the process. Both psychologists and designers stepped out of their own professional sphere: designers questioning the theory, psychologists reacting on design sketches. Both contributed to the translation of theory to insights in human behaviour, to interaction with products, to product characteristics; not in a simple straightforward process, but in iterations. Design students used their design output (such as criteria,

scenarios, design sketches) as embodiments of their notions on the theory. The psychologists then used these materials to recognize (mis-)conceptions, and as starting points to discuss elements of the theory and relations between them and the consequences for the dynamics of the resulting play behaviour. Through this they again challenged and inspired the students to adopt their designs to reflect a more comprehensive view on the theory.

It has been a true dialogue, one in which students used design as their language. It has been in this dialogue that the following six themes have become apparent.

INVOLVEMENT

Students are willing and indeed enthusiastic about trying out the value of new theories for their design thinking. Being educated as generalists who need to collect and integrate specialist information in each different project, they easily accept the theories as a possible tool for analysis and a source of understanding child behaviour.

This was underlined by the motivation of students to get as much information as they could from the psychologists. After a first lecture-based introduction of the theory, one class of 20 students sent in over 30 different questions to the psychologists to be answered in a subsequent lecture. These questions covered a wide range of aspects, and made the psychologists wish for the same uninhibited curiosity in their regular psychology students.

Some examples of questions are worth a closer look.

“Why does the paratelic curve not start at the cross-section of axis?” (see Figure 1)

This question, though simple at first sight, uncovers how more technically oriented design students read the figure as a mathematical graph rather than a visual representation of a psychological theory. Questions like these enabled the psychologists to reflect with students on the difference in studying behaviour as objectively measurable performance vs. subjective experience.

“As a child, I kept a dead dragonfly in a transparent plastic box. I shivered at the close-by look of its head and body, but I kept coming back to look at it;

it was a nice kind of fear. Is this explained by Reversal Theory as well?"

Questions like these showed how students tried to familiarise themselves with the theory through linking it to their own experiences - and checking if they understood it correctly.

Many questions demonstrated the immediate attempts of students to relate the theory to the design task at hand. The discussions that followed from it strengthened confidence in the usefulness of the theory, stimulating the students to delve deeper into it.

FRAGMENTATION OF THE THEORY

Students demonstrated difficulty in dealing with the theory as a holistic perspective. Many of them reduced the theory to somewhat primitive guidelines and then treated them as unconnected phenomena. An example is the following student question:

"How can a game be kept interesting for children when the maximum amount of arousal has already been reached?"

Another example is a student's idea that a toy will automatically switch a user into the paratelic mode so that the possible switch to the telic mode wouldn't be of any concern for design.

A large part of the psychologists' effort was directed at stimulating the development of a more coherent overall treatment of the theory, rather than such a fragmented one.

DEALING WITH SUBJECTIVITY

The theory discerns between modes or states of mind. These are subjective phenomena, e.g. a 'fearful' situation is only perceived as fearful by those who are susceptible to its dangerous characteristics. One cannot determine such a state of mind.

In the psychological discourse, it may be common knowledge that any description of psychological states refers to a possibility or probability of a person being in that state, but many design students attempted to apply theory prescriptively. They didn't fully realise that designers are merely able to

design for the probability that an object might be used, or experienced, in a certain way. Many students declared themselves the rulers of the users' emotions rather than more modest influencers. They overlooked the subjectivity and individual dynamic that was apparent in the theory as well as the variety of responses between individuals. An example of this is given in the next subsection on 'schematic thinking'.

SCHEMATIC THINKING

As with most psychology theories, this theory describes processes and operations; dynamic situations of change. These changes have extremes (from being unable to mastering, from excitement to anxiety, etc.) that are easily recognizable but the more subtle in-between states were easily overlooked by students. This oversimplified, schematic way of thinking was evident in some of the design proposals. One example is the spinning water toy (Figure 2).

It consists of a water bottle that is connected to a spinning spray mouth. After the bottle is filled with water and connected, air is pumped into the bottle. The spray mouth starts to spray water and spin around, until the bottle comes loose and shoots off like a rocket. By kicking the pedal that spins around the bottle, players can influence the angle of the water mouth and thus the height of the water jet.

Figure 2: Spinning water toy. The red lines give a hint of the variety in directions the water jet can take. Design by Bob van den Meiracker and Sander van Roosmalen.

In an early version, the students had defined the start situation, the amount and position of the players around the toy, and a system to define who was the winner of the game. Through this elaborate set of behavioural rule-based instructions, the degrees of freedom for the players were restricted. It meant that one was either in or out of the game,

able or unable to avoid getting wet and targeting the others, etc. After discussions about the probability of reversal between telic and paratelic states of mind, it became clear to the students that it was wiser to reduce rules and give players the authority and choice in how to be involved (and self-regulate their arousal); as observers, intermittent players, or fully engaged; challenging each other or cooperating to control the toy; or in other ways that might naturally come to the players minds. This enables each player to control the amount of arousal she experiences, and over the subjective level of risks she runs - thereby creating bandwidth to find the experience that prevents reversal into a telic mode by either being bored or frightened.

DESIGNING FOR EMOTIONAL STATES

If typically students focus on toys as tools for an activity, and often consider pleasantness or 'fun' as a function of the activity, Reversal Theory made them reflect more on the function of a toy as a tool for active self-regulation of more complex emotional and motivational states.

Figure 3 shows the design of a museum toy. The aim here was to create an experience of quietness and recharging within the hectic atmosphere of a children's museum. The product shown is a colour filter that needs to be held in the hands and pushed against the walls and floor of one room to reveal a very detailed graphical storyline. All elements of the toy are directed towards bringing the child close to the walls, slowing down movements, studying the details and focusing on what is visible within the small frame.

In their description of the use of the toy, the students mention that the almost meditative quality of the experience is encouraged by reducing the state of arousal of the child: they argue that all the design decisions are directed towards slow, gradual, focused, solitary, quiet behaviour. Here, the pursued emotional state of the child is leading and the play activities follow from it.

INSPIRATION

Earlier, it has been mentioned that students found it difficult to perceive the theory as a holistic perspective and took parts of the theory as separate guidelines. Even then students found, if not a

Figure 3: The quiet museum toy consists of red and green filter frames (above), patterns of green and red in which drawings are hidden (middle) cover the walls and floor, making children crawl around with the frames to discover story-lines (below). Design by Chandra Rinie Pudjiatie and Novi Rahman.

coherent new perspective, at least parts of explanations for child behaviour and play needs that they otherwise would have stayed ignorant of. It is clear that in these cases the theory did sparkle and guide their creativity in unforeseen directions. For instance, the seven strategies for creating arousal mentioned in Table 1 provided such direct pointers for design directions - whether linked to the core of the theory or not. The tendency in working with these seven strategies was to take the ones that were most easily understandable or most clearly related to arousal. One group chose 'exposure to arousing stimulation' and 'accepting a challenge' as

a base for their ideation - and found themselves stuck with ideas that were lacking in originality. After being confronted by the psychologists with the limited creative spark from their safe choices, they decided to explore others as well, especially 'negativism'; deliberate rule-breaking, often in provocative ways. Their designs immediately got more intriguing, partly because of their irresponsible nature. The students experienced the attractiveness of their proposed activities, stayed in touch with it during the consequent phase of attuning it to practical limitations of safety and social acceptability, and came up with something weird and thought-provoking: the bottle-bank that invites you to throw and smash your empty glass bottles (Figure 4). Different colours glass go in different toss lanes, with different screens at the far end: one that is transparent and allows the child to throw a bottle at another child standing behind the screen, one that allows the child to record the sound of shattering glass and play with the sounds, and one that depicts blots of different colours depending on the impact of the throw.

Figure 4: Bottle bank. Design by Alen Halilovic and Ruben Rosenbrand.

An interesting side effect of the design is that waste becomes something valuable and scarce. Children that like this sort of play may even go door-to-door in the neighbourhood collecting the empty bottles. Of course, the idea is still rough and would need a lot of consideration on safety issues and careful planning of location. The point here is that an idea like this clearly evolved from a not so mainstream element of Reversal Theory; and that it pointed the students towards an area they had not allowed themselves to explore before.

DISCUSSION

The project described in this paper was undertaken with the intention to explore the dialogue between designers and psychologists within a design context, with the aim to help designers understand theoretic frameworks that are new within the design context and thereby widening their arena for design solutions that cater for people's needs - in this case, the arena of tools for playful behaviour.

On the basis of the exploration described in this paper, the dialogue between social sciences and design can certainly be regarded as beneficial to design.

It was observed how the designers went through interest, puzzlement, sometimes frustration, to appreciation when finally they got a grip on the theory. It gave them a broader insight in playful behaviour and a sense of control over it - control by allowing self-governance of the player rather than prescribing behaviour.

If this resulted in design ideas that are different from what they would otherwise have created, remains speculative. As stated before, no formal assessment of the design outcome has been made. It was observed how understanding elements of the theory led to, sometimes radical, changes in idea development. On other occasions, other students have been able to create novel ideas without using this theory. Yet it is observed that the theory supported insights and through that empowered them to reach beyond the all too familiar toy concepts. The example of the glass bank indicates that designers were able to broaden their view on how playfulness is not in what you do, but how you do it, and how danger and anxiety can be brought under control and lead to pleasurable experiences. The experience with coaching toy design students over a number of years is that play as an activity can be so diverse and gives so little direction, that students easily fall back on existing examples and proven concepts for support and inspiration. Bringing a theory to this domain that helps creating and recognizing potential for playful behaviour certainly broadened the designers' toolkit.

The productive contribution of design work by the students proved helpful for the psychologists to understand what the difficulties are for designers in

applying the theory. This helped them to focus their guidance on those aspects.

The psychologists recognized that teaching this theory within a context where direct application is the aim contributed to the motivation and involvement of the students. They even considered giving design tasks to their own psychology students as an educational instrument. It would be interesting to see how fluent these students would be in the design language and how the effects would compare to those of the design students.

It can be questioned to what extent designers need to understand the theory. They cannot be expected to become fully educated psychologists themselves. From the experiences in this project, it is learned that designers had the tendency to use elements of the theory separately - in an unconnected way. It was seen a number of times that students singled out an element of theory they understood best, blinding themselves for the implications of the extended theory. They may be inspired by one psychological concept, but if they don't understand how various concepts interrelate within the structure of the theory, the validity of the outcome may be disputable.

In this respect, it is interesting to broaden the search described in this paper towards an exploration of what the criteria could be for psychological theory from a design point of view; e.g. how could and should psychological theories be (re)phrased and presented to support the dialogue with the design discipline?

CONCLUSION

The experience of designing children's playful products inspired by a relatively unexplored psychological theory in this project shows the value of sustained dialogue. Students use the design arena, in which they feel confident, to translate and apply their notions of the theories. Psychologists can use the students' design work to recognize the flaws and misconceptions that wouldn't be uncovered if they both had stayed within the theoretic discourse. Design in this sense is an integral part of the dialogue.

Together, psychologists and designers can assure that the knowledge about lesser-known theories translates into inspiration for design, releasing a new potential for children's play products that cater for children's authentic needs.

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